

PROBLEMS AND CHALLENGES OF ZAKAT IMPLEMENTATION AND ITS MANAGEMENT TO REDUCE ECONOMIC GAP

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Abstract

Zakat is the shariah or the rule of Allah SWT. which are universal, conceptual and ideal. The idealism of zakat rules is to create a prosperous, just and equitable society. Conditions like this will certainly make the members of the community feel safe, comfortable, and orderly. Although the command of zakat is mentioned in the Qur'an and the hadith of the Prophet SAW and reinforced by government regulations, but in reality there are still many Muslims who neglect this noble obligation. Economic gap is still strongly felt in people's lives. The number of Indonesians who have income below the poverty line is about 27.77 million people. In fact, the potential of zakat in Indonesia shows a very fantastic figure. National Amil Zakat Agency (BAZNAS) and IPB in research in 2012 stated that the national zakat potential is estimated to reach Rp 217 trillion per year. However, the report of zakat receipts in 2011 by zakat management institutions in Indonesia, namely BAZNAS, BAZ Regional and Lembaga Amil Zakat (LAZ) only collected Rp. 1.8 Trillion. Among the issues that impede the implementation and management of zakat are the understanding and awareness of the people about zakat, the rigid understanding of amilin about zakat and their lack of competence and professionalism, low public trust in zakat institutions, traditional and improper distribution of zakat, lack of technological support and information systems, and the mental attitude of the mustahik.

Preliminary

Zakat is one of the main teachings in Islam. He is one of the pillars of the upholding of Islam in a person. As the saying of Prophet Muhammad SAW, *"Islam was founded on five pillars. First, testified that no one deserves to be worshiped but Allah Almighty. Two, establish the prayers. Third, the zakat. Fourth, fasting in Ramadan. Fifth, performing the pilgrimage to the baitullah for capable people."* (Muttafaqun 'alaih).

The scholars have agreed on the obligation of zakat upon every qualified Muslim, Allah SWT. explicitly ordered to take some of the property of someone who is bound by Islamic law (mukallaf) and his property has exceeded the minimum limit to be issued of zakat. His word in the Qur'an surah At-Taubah: 103, *"Take alms from some of their treasures which will cleanse and purify them."* The verse implies that the treasure that Allah granted to a person does not mean to have it fully. There is a rule of Allah SWT to distribute some property to others who need it more. By distributing a portion of the property to the needy, the treasures and souls of the distributors become clean and holy. On the contrary, if the treasure is dumped without being issued of the zakat, then there is "dirt" treasures that are not cleaned that will damage the soul and other property. It is not wrong that the notion of zakat is growing, sacred, and blessing. In another verse, Allah Almighty. Explains that zakat will bring pleasure to the culprit. His word, *"Verily they will dwell in the gardens of heaven and the springs. They receive the gift from their Lord. In the past (in the world) they were good people, they only closed their eyes for a while at night, at the end of the night (they woke up) and asked for forgiveness, and they set aside some of their property for the asker and the one who did not have "*. (Surah Adz-Dzariyat: 15-19).

In addition to the verses of the Qur'an, there are hadiths of the Prophet Saw. Which contains the advice for zakat. Among his SAW sayings when sending Mu'adz bin Jabal to become a judge in Yemen. *"O Mu'adz, surely you will come to a people of the group of scribes, then call*

them first to testify that there is no right to be worshiped except Allah, and I am His messenger. If they will do that, teach them that Allah Almighty. Has obliged prayers five times a day a night. If they obey it, say that Allah Almighty. Obliging zakat on their possessions levied from the rich and given to the poor among them". (HR Jama'ah).

In the books of Al-Ausath and Ash-Shaghir, Thabrani narrates about the importance of zakat from Ali bin Abi Talib that the Messenger of Allah. Said, "Allah SWT. obligate zakat on the part of wealth of the rich people of the Muslims in order to meet the needs of the pauper among them. Surely those poor people will not suffer hunger and hardship, but because of the deeds of the rich. Remember! That Allah will judge them later firmly and torment them with pain."

Zakat is the Shariah or the rule of Allah SWT. Which are universal, conceptual and ideal. The idealism of zakat rules is to create a prosperous, just, and equitable society. Conditions like this will certainly make the members of the community feel safe, comfortable, and orderly. Thus, this zakat not only creates a vertically good relationship between man and Allah, but also creates a horizontal relationship between people. Therefore, the implementation of zakat is not only within the private sphere of the individual, but in the public space.

Then how the implementation of zakat that has entered the public level in a state institution? In this case, the government issues the rules in consideration letter b of Law no. 23 of 2011 on the Management of Zakat stating that the fulfillment of zakat is an obligation for Muslims. Zakat is a religious institution that aims to improve justice, community welfare, and poverty alleviation.

Challenges of Implementation and Management of Zakat

Although the command of zakat is mentioned in the Qur'an and the hadith of the Prophet. And reinforced by government regulations, but in reality there are still many Muslims who neglect this noble obligation. Economic gap are still strongly felt in people's lives. Economic disparity is a serious problem because of the devastating impact it generates on society, nation and state. The gap between the rich and the poor which is too far away can lead to social inequality, then grow social jealousy and social hatred. In this stage of social hatred, a society can be easily induced until a social conflict sparked to a greater extent can trigger the disintegration of the nation.

According to BPS data, the number of poor people in Indonesia in 2017 with poverty line limit of Rp. 385,621 / capita / month is 27, 77 million people with a percentage of 10.64%. In full, the data on the number of poor, the percentage of the poor and the poverty line between 2011-2017 are presented in the following table.

Tabel 1. Total of Poor People, Percentage of Poor People, and Poverty Condition, 2011-2017

Year	Total of Poor People (in million people)			Percentage of Poor People			Poverty Condition (Rp/Capital/Month)	
	City	Village	City+Village	City	Village	City+Village	City	Village
Maret 2011	11.05	18.97	30.02	9.23	15.72	12.49	253 016	213 395
September 2011	10.95	18.94	29.89	9.09	15.59	12.36	263 594	223 181
Maret 2012	10.65	18.49	29.13	8.78	15.12	11.96	267 408	229 226
September 2012	10.51	18.09	28.59	8.60	14.70	11.66	277 382	240 441
Maret 2013	10.33	17.74	28.07	8.39	14.32	11.37	289 042	253 273
September 2013	10.63	17.92	28.55	8.52	14.42	11.47	308 826	275 779
Maret 2014	10.51	17.77	28.28	8.34	14.17	11.25	318 514	286 097

September 2014	10.36	17.37	27.73	8.16	13.76	10.96	326 853	296 681
Maret 2015	10.65	17.94	28.59	8.29	14.21	11.22	342 541	317 881
September 2015	10.62	17.89	28.51	8.22	14.09	11.13	356 378	333 034
Maret 2016	10.34	17.67	28.01	7.79	14.11	10.86	364 527	343 647
September 2016	10.49	17.28	27.76	7.73	13.96	10.70	372 114	350 420
Maret 2017	10.67	17.10	27.77	7.72	13.93	10.64	385 621	361 496

From the data above, especially on the poverty line column (income / capita / month) shows that the number of Indonesians who have income below the poverty line is approximately 27.77 million people. This is certainly very worrying. In fact, the potential of zakat in Indonesia shows a very fantastic figure. National Amil Zakat Agency (BAZNAS) and IPB in research in 2012 stated that the national zakat potential is estimated to reach Rp 217 trillion per year. However, the report of zakat receipts in 2011 by zakat management institutions in Indonesia, namely BAZNAS, BAZ Regional and Lembaga Amil Zakat (LAZ) only collected Rp. 1.8 Trillion. It is unfortunate that the huge potential of zakat cannot be explored to the maximum so that it has not been able to alleviate poverty in Indonesia. (Norvadewi: 2012).

The Problems in the Implementation and Management of Zakat

Judging from the fact that the number of poor people is still significant, the perfect divine concept of zakat to alleviate poverty seems not to be implemented properly. Among the issues that impede the implementation and management of zakat are as follows.

1. Community understanding and awareness about zakat

Most people have an understanding that zakat is the shari'ah of Islam and its implementation must be in accordance with the Qur'anic text and the hadith of the Prophet. Armed with this understanding, there is a group of people who believe in the absence of zakat profession because there is no text in the Qur'an and hadith that states it explicitly. This is stated by Hafidhuddin that one of the causes of not optimally yet in collection of zakat and has not felt its function because the knowledge and public understanding of the zakat obligatory is still limited to the conventional sources clearly stated in the Qur'an and hadith with certain requirements.

In addition, public awareness to pay zakat is still lacking. Many people still enjoy to show their wealth rather than paying zakat. They prefer to repay the car or other goods rather than prioritize paying zakat.

2. A rigid understanding about Islamic jurisprudence (fikih) of amilin and their lack of competence and professionalism.

Not only people who have a rigid understanding of religious jurisprudence, but not a few amil who understand the postulates of the zakat and rules textually. Contextual understanding of the propositions of zakat can bring zakat closer to the core concepts of the shari'ah of zakat, namely economic equity, economic empowerment of people, and purification of the human soul from greed to property. The distribution of zakat must be beneficial to the people and capable of making it impossible to become an independent and economically empowered individual.

Based on the observations made by Norvadewi on several zakat institutions, especially those managed by the government, she sees the weakness of the professional aspects of zakat management. Human resources management zakat recruited without competitive selection, even the elements of collusion and nepotism in recruitment is still quite thick so that the professionalism and sincerity in managing zakat is still low.

While on the other hand, the job of being an amil zakat has not become a coveted profession. Scholars of shariah economics are more inclined to career in the banking and insurance sector and less glance at the job of being amil in zakat amil institutions. Ideally, amil

institutions are filled with qualified human resources for the management of zakat can be professional, trustworthy, accountable, and transparent.

3. Low public trust on zakat institutions

Among the members of the community feel more satisfied to distribute their zakat individually. This is reinforced by the opinion of scholars in the classical Jurisprudence that zakat is more important if it is submitted directly to mustahik. Hamy Wahjunianto, Chairman of Zakat Forum (FOZ) reinforces the assumption. He cited the public trust of the community-formed zakat institution (LAZ) much stronger than the government-formed zakat institution (BAZ). This is evidenced by the accumulation of ZIS by LAZ greater than the collection by BAZ, as well as the number of donors and muzakki. The direct distribution by individuals to those around him who are deemed qualified as mustahik is not wrong. However, in the perspective of professional zakat management, it is less effective.

4. Traditional and improper distribution of zakat

Zakat managers are still many who think that zakat must be distributed to the mustahik. The receipt of zakat is distributed to a number of mustahik with a value that is almost flat with the assumption of justice and all mustahik get a share. Mustahik usually use what they get for consumptive needs. This kind of channeling can indeed help the mustahik to meet the urgent needs of daily needs. However, this way tends to make the mustahik the poor need to remain in a state of poverty. Zakat should be able to empower and encourage the poor to be more productive.

5. Lack of technological support and information systems

Technology and information systems is a very supportive tool in storing data and discipline administration. Information technology and systems related to zakat management such as computer, internet, mobile phone, mobile zakat, zakat card, and supporting information system application are very important in the digital era. The management of zakat that does not adapt to the condition of the digital society as it is now will hinder the implementation of zakat and the achievement of the purpose of zakat.

6. The mental attitude of the mustahik

Mental attitudes are behaviors that are born from a person's psychological condition. A mental state that expects only the giving of others and does not want to try to change the state of itself will be difficult to escape from the shackles of poverty. How much help is provided will not change the condition of the person who has the begging spirit.

Suggestion

The above problems require solutions for better implementation and management of zakat. Among the solutions that can be offered to overcome the problems of zakat is as follows.

1. Socializing contemporary zakat fiqh through lectures, print media, and electronic media to increase public understanding about zakat and innovations of zakat implementation. Increasing people's understanding about zakat is expected to increase public awareness and enthusiasm to fulfill zakat.

2. Conducting coaching and training on amil zakat. The amil zakat is an important component in the management of zakat. Amil as the executor ideally has good understanding of jurisprudence about zakat so that he is not rigid, flexible without going beyond the rules of shari'ah. Amil can be an agent to provide socialization of knowledge to the public about zakat.

3. Increasing public trust in zakat institution with transparency of acceptance and distribution of zakat. Such reports may be published on line via the website of the relevant zakat institution. The full presentation of the report will lead people to believe in the zakat management agency.

4. Distribution of zakat appropriate and appropriate target. Zakat should not only be distributed in the form of money and consumer goods only, but can also in the form of facilities and infrastructure that can stimulate the growth of economic power of society. For example, machines, carts that can be used for selling, training and coaching in production and distribution, and others in accordance with the potential that exists in the community of a region. In the case of distribution of zakat, the Ministry of Religious Affairs affirmed in its decision no. 373 of 2003 on "The procedures for utilizing the results of zakat collection for productive enterprises are stipulated as

follows: (1) conducting a feasibility study; (2) to determine the type of productive enterprise; (3) conducting guidance and counseling; (4) conduct monitoring, control and supervision; (5) conduct evaluation and (6) make reporting.

5. Technology and information systems that support the management of zakat. Technology and information systems in the digital age has become a necessity in every managerial activity. No exception in zakat management. The input and output of zakat funds must be managed well in order to realize the purpose of zakat. Alhamdulillah, according to information from the BAZNAS website, since 2013, BAZNAS has successfully developed an online information management system based on the name of SiMBA. SiMBA which stands for BAZNAS Information Management System is an information system that can assist BAZNAS (central, provincial, district / city) and LAZ operations in an information management system that can generate reports that are tiered from district to province, from province to center, And from the center to the President / DPR. With this information system, it is expected to create a transparent and accountable management system of zakat throughout Indonesia.

6. The mental construction of the mustahik to become muzakki. Assistance to mustahik is not only material, but immaterial is quite important, including mental coaching. The mustahik mindset must be changed so that they have a high work ethic.

Conclusion

Zakat is the Shari'ah which Allah Almighty decreed. Over Muslims to alleviate poverty, reduce economic disparities in society, and assist in the realization of a society that is pious, prosperous, just and prosperous. In practice, many challenges and problems that need solutions to achieve the goals of this shariah zakat. The challenges and problems are impassable except by equating vision and action together.

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